

Application of ammonium hexanitratocerate(IV) for the determination of some antibiotics

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Abstract : A simple and convenient method has been developed for milligram determination of some Antibiotic drugs e.g. Amoxicillin sodium, Ampicillin, Cefixime, Cloxacillin sodium, Norfloxacin and Ornidazole in pure form and in their pharmaceutical preparations. The method involves the oxidation of compounds with 0.1 M ammonium hexanitratocerate(IV) reagent in acidic medium. Aliquots containing 1–5 mg of samples were taken in a 100 ml conical flask and 5 mL of 0.1 M reagent and 10 mL of 1 M H₂SO₄ were added to it. The contents were shaken well and allowed to react at room temperature (25–30 °C) for the required reaction time (10–15 min). After the reaction was over, the contents were titrated with ferrous ammonium sulphate solution (0.025 M) using 0.001 M ferroin indicator. A blank experiment was also run under identical condition using all the reagents except the sample. The same procedure was applied for their pharmaceutical preparations. It was noted that the excipients present in pharmaceutical preparation do not interfere in the determination. The value of percentage error, coefficient of variation (CV) and standard deviation (SD) prove the method to be precise and reproducible. To establish authenticity of the methods, recovery experiments were carried out by standard drug addition method. Indian Pharmacopoeia does not describe such simple methods; moreover their methods are for individual compounds and not for all the compounds.

Keywords : Antibiotics, pharmaceuticals, ammonium hexanitratocerate(IV), titration.

Introduction

Many micro-organisms produce within themselves chemical substances which whenever created, interfere with the growth or metabolism of other micro-organism. Such compounds are called antibiotics. These are chemical substance which can inhibit the growth of other micro-organism or may even destroy them. Amoxicillin is closely related to Ampicillin and both are used to treat urinary tract infections, uncomplicated community-acquired pneumonia, *Haemophilus influenzae*, *Salmonellosis* and *Listeria meningitis*. Antibiotic do not work for colds, flu, or other viral infections. Cefixime is a cephalosporin group of antibiotic used to treat respiratory tract infections, middle ear infections, skin infections, urinary tract infections and tonsillitis. Cloxacillin is a penicillin group of antibiotic and commonly used to treat infections of the skin, bone, heart valve, blood, and throat. Norfloxacin belongs to quinoline group of antibiotics. It works in stopping the growth of bacteria and is also used to treat other health care provider. Ornidazole is used to

cure protozoans infections like crohn's disease after bowel resection. Because of great medicinal value of these compounds their estimation has widely been studied¹⁻¹⁵. Most of the above methods involve sophisticated instruments and complicated techniques. In the present paper we describe a simple and convenient method for the determination of above antibiotics with ammonium hexanitratocerate(IV) reagent. The method is applicable in those pharmaceutical laboratories where modern instruments are not available.

Experimental

Reagent and solutions :

0.1 M Ammonium hexanitratocerate (AHC) solution : 13.70 g of ammonium hexanitratocerate(IV) (AnalaR, Qualigens) was weighed accurately and dissolved in 0.5 N nitric acid in a 250 mL volumetric flask.

0.025 M Ferrous ammonium sulphate solution : 2.4508 g of ferrous ammonium sulphate (Merck) was accurately weighed and dissolved in distilled water in the presence

of 10 ml of 4 M H₂SO₄ in a 250 mL volumetric flask.

0.001 M Ferroin indicator : Solution was prepared by diluting 0.025 M ferroin (1,10-phenanthroline ferrous sulphate complex) solution with distilled water.

1 M and 4 M sulphuric acid solution : Solutions were prepared by diluting concentrated sulphuric acid (37 N AnalaR, Merck) with distilled water.

Sample solutions (1 mg/mL) : Accurately weighed (100 mg) Ampicillin (pure), Cefixime (pure), Cloxacillin sodium (pure) and Ornidazole (pure) were dissolved in distilled water in a 100 mL volumetric flask. Amoxicillin and Norfloxacin were first dissolved in min. amount of dil. H₂SO₄ in a 100 mL volumetric flask and then made up to the mark with distilled water to give a concentration of 1 mg/mL.

Tablets solution : Twenty tablets of a particular sample were crushed to a fine powder and powder equivalent to 100 mg of sample was taken in 100 mL volumetric flask and dissolved similarly. No residue was noted in any of

the samples.

Injections solution : Injections solutions were also prepared similarly to give a concentration of 1 mg/mL.

Procedure : Aliquots containing 1–5 mg of the samples were taken in 100 mL stoppered conical flask followed by the addition of 5 mL AHC reagent. The reaction mixture was shaken well and allowed to react for required reaction time (10–15 min) at room temperature (25–30 °C). After the reaction was over it was quenched by adding 10 mL of 1 M sulphuric acid. The unconsumed Ce^{IV} was titrated against 0.025 M ferrous ammonium sulphate solution using two drops of ferroin indicator (0.001 M). A blank experiment was also performed under identical conditions using all the reagents except the sample. The amount of the sample was calculated by the following expression. On the basis of percentage error the value of SD and CV were also calculated (Table 1). In the case of pharmaceutical preparation the same procedure was applied. It was observed that the excipients present in pharmaceuticals do not interfere.

Table 1. Determination of some antibiotic drugs in pure form and in their pharmaceutical preparations with (0.1 M) ammonium hexanitratocerate(IV) reagent

Sl. no.	Sample	Aliquots taken (mL)	Amount present ^a (mg)	Reaction time (min)	Molecularity	Amount obtained by calculation ^b (mg)	Error (%)	SD (±)	CV
1.	Amoxicillin (pure)	1.00	0.996	15	6	0.986	1.00	0.0019	0.1927
		3.00	2.988			2.968	0.67	0.0046	0.1550
		5.00	4.980			4.956	0.48	0.0024	0.0484
	(A) Novamox-DT (Tab) Cipla	1.00	0.937	15	6	0.927	1.07	0.0015	0.1618
		3.00	2.811			2.792	0.68	0.0026	0.0931
		5.00	4.685			4.661	0.51	0.0041	0.0880
	(B) Blumox-DT (Tab) Blue Cross	1.00	0.941	15	6	0.931	1.06	0.0015	0.1611
		3.00	2.823			2.805	0.64	0.0014	0.0499
		5.00	4.705			4.686	0.40	0.0025	0.0534
2.	Ampicillin (pure)	1.00	0.986	15	6	0.976	1.01	0.0038	0.3893
		3.00	2.958			2.936	0.74	0.0020	0.0681
		5.00	4.930			4.909	0.43	0.0026	0.0530
	(A) Cincillin (Inj) Ind-swift	1.00	0.913	15	6	0.903	1.00	0.0027	0.2990
		3.00	2.739			2.722	0.62	0.0024	0.0024
		5.00	4.565			4.546	0.42	0.0022	0.0484
	(B) Roscillin (Inj) Neon Labs	1.00	0.924	15	6	0.914	1.08	0.0017	0.1860
		3.00	2.772			2.750	0.79	0.0025	0.0909
		5.00	4.620			4.604	0.35	0.0039	0.0847

Table-1 (contd.)

3.	Cefixime (pure)	1.00	0.978			0.968	1.02	0.0019	0.1963
		3.00	2.934	15	4	2.916	0.61	0.0028	0.0960
		5.00	4.890			4.872	0.37	0.0038	0.0780
(A) Cefexy (Tab)	Neiss	1.00	0.905			0.895	1.10	0.0022	0.2458
		3.00	2.715	15	4	2.695	0.74	0.0036	0.1336
		5.00	4.525			4.501	0.53	0.0028	0.0622
(B) Hifen (Tab)	Hetro HC	1.00	0.912			0.902	1.10	0.0034	0.3769
		3.00	2.736	15	4	2.718	0.66	0.0028	0.1030
		5.00	4.560			4.543	0.37	0.0041	0.0902
4.	Cloxacillin sodium (pure)	1.00	0.959			0.949	1.04	0.0021	0.2213
		3.00	2.877	10	4	2.859	0.63	0.0019	0.0665
		5.00	4.795			4.775	0.42	0.0038	0.0796
(A) Klox (Inj)	Hetero HC	1.00	0.928			0.918	1.06	0.0026	0.2832
		3.00	2.784	10	4	2.763	0.75	0.0034	0.1231
		5.00	4.640			4.621	0.41	0.0032	0.0692
(B) Neoclox (Tab)	Neon Labs	1.00	0.921			0.911	1.09	0.0029	0.3183
		3.00	2.763	10	4	2.746	0.62	0.0040	0.1457
		5.00	4.605			4.590	0.33	0.0036	0.0784
5.	Norfloxacin (pure)	1.00	0.965			0.955	1.04	0.0039	0.4084
		3.00	2.895	10	6	2.875	0.69	0.0035	0.1217
		5.00	4.825			4.804	0.44	0.0040	0.0833
(A) Uflox (Tab)	Bal Pharma	1.00	0.926			0.916	1.08	0.0020	0.2183
		3.00	2.778	10	6	2.759	0.68	0.0022	0.0797
		5.00	4.630			4.612	0.39	0.0037	0.0802
(B) Utibid (Tab)	Lupin	1.00	0.938			0.928	1.07	0.0019	0.2047
		3.00	2.814	10	6	2.795	0.68	0.0025	0.0894
		5.00	4.690			4.674	0.34	0.0032	0.0685
6.	Ornidazole (pure)	1.00	0.983			0.973	1.02	0.0026	0.2672
		3.00	2.949	15	4	2.931	0.61	0.0018	0.0614
		5.00	4.915			4.894	0.43	0.0030	0.0613
(A) Giro (Tab)	Panacea	1.00	0.953			0.943	1.05	0.0019	0.2015
		3.00	2.859	15	4	2.839	0.70	0.0022	0.0775
		5.00	4.765			4.746	0.40	0.0028	0.059
(B) Ornilox (Tab)	Micro Labs	1.00	0.932			0.922	1.07	0.0021	0.2278
		3.00	2.796	15	4	2.778	0.64	0.0022	0.0792
		5.00	4.660			4.642	0.39	0.0033	0.0711

Tab = Tablet, Inj = Injection, SD= Standard deviation, CV= Coefficient of variation.

^aIn each sample nine estimations were done. ^bAverage of nine determinations.

Calculation :

$$\text{mg of sample} = \frac{M \times N (B - S)}{n}$$

where, *M* = molecular weight of sample, *N* = normality of ferrous ammonium sulphate solution, *B* = volume of ferrous ammonium sulphate for blank, *S* = volume of

ferrous ammonium sulphate for sample, *n* = no. of moles of ammonium hexanitratocerate(IV) consumed per mol of the sample.

Results and discussion

The reaction conditions were established after studying the effect of variables such as reaction time, concen-

tration and volume of ammonium hexanitratocerate(IV) reagent, concentration and volume of sulphuric acid and reaction temperature. In the determination of amoxicillin, ampicillin, cefixime and ornidazole 15 min reaction time was needed to complete the reaction while cloxacillin sodium and norfloxacin requires only 10 min. A much more reaction time beyond (10–15 min) does not improve the results. At lower reaction time (less than 10 min) the recovery of the sample was low because of the incomplete reaction. It was also established that the prescribed concentration of the reagent (0.1 M) was suitable for accurate results. An increase in the concentration of the reagents (0.1–1.0 M) does not have any effects on the recovery. A lower concentration (0.1–0.01 M) gives inaccurate results because of incomplete reaction. While studying the effect of concentration of sulphuric acid it was found that recommended (4 M) concentration and volume (10 mL) of the acid was suitable for the reaction. While studying the effect of reaction temperature it was noticed that the reaction was complete at room temperature (25–30 °C). On heating the reaction mixture either

on water bath or directly on flame gives inaccurate results. If the reaction was carried out at lower temperature (0–15 °C) the speed of the reaction was much more retarded. On increasing reaction time (15–40 min) there was no effect on the percentage recovery.

Results of estimations are reported in Table 1. To test the precision of the method recovery experiments were done by standard drug addition method (Tables 2–7). It shows that the suggested method is accurate reproducible and precise. It can easily be adopted in ordinary pharmaceutical laboratory where sophisticated instruments are not available. On the basis of molecularity, available literature a possible course of reaction may be suggested for each compounds. Since isolation of the final reaction products and their identification has not been possible, it may be proposed that the compounds get oxidized to suitable corresponding oxidized products. Indian Pharmacopoeia does not describe a general method for determination of above antibiotics. However there are methods for individual compounds e.g. amoxicillin sodium, ampicil-

Table 2. Recovery studies of Amoxicillin by standard drug addition method

Sl. no.	Number of observations (N)	Amount present (pure) (mg)	Amount of drug added (mg)	Total amount of drug obtained by calculation (mg)	Amount of drug obtained by calculation (mg)	XY	X ²	Recovery (%)
			X	(mg)	Y			
1.	3	0.996	0.978	1.975	0.993	0.971	0.956	
2.	3	0.996	1.964	2.970	1.979	3.887	3.857	
3.	3	0.996	2.960	3.986	2.865	8.480	8.762	99.34
4.	3	0.996	3.958	4.990	3.972	15.721	15.666	
	$\Sigma N = 12$		$\Sigma X = 9.860$		$\Sigma Y = 9.809$	$\Sigma XY = 29.059$	$\Sigma X^2 = 29.241$	

Table 3. Recovery studies of Ampicillin by standard drug addition method

Sl. no.	Number of observations (N)	Amount present (pure) (mg)	Amount of drug added (mg)	Total amount of drug obtained by calculation (mg)	Amount of drug obtained by calculation (mg)	XY	X ²	Recovery (%)
			X	(mg)	Y			
1.	3	0.986	0.981	1.970	0.990	0.971	0.962	
2.	3	0.986	1.963	2.969	1.980	3.887	3.853	
3.	3	0.986	2.961	3.985	2.864	8.480	8.768	99.04
4.	3	0.986	3.956	4.989	3.974	15.721	15.721	
	$\Sigma N = 12$		$\Sigma X = 9.861$		$\Sigma Y = 9.808$	$\Sigma XY = 29.059$	$\Sigma X^2 = 29.304$	

Table 4. Recovery studies of Cefixime by standard drug addition method

Sl. no.	Number of observations (N)	Amount present (pure) (mg)	Amount of drug added (mg)	Total amount of drug obtained by calculation (mg)	Amount of drug obtained by calculation (mg)	XY	X ²	Recovery (%)
			X	(mg)	Y			
1.	3	0.978	0.982	1.978	0.989	0.971	0.964	
2.	3	0.978	1.967	2.985	1.976	3.887	3.869	
3.	3	0.978	2.958	3.972	2.867	8.481	8.750	99.26
4.	3	0.978	3.962	4.979	3.970	15.729	15.697	
	$\Sigma N = 12$		$\Sigma X = 9.869$		$\Sigma Y = 9.802$	$\Sigma XY = 29.068$	$\Sigma X^2 = 29.280$	

Table 5. Recovery studies of Cloxacillin sodium by standard drug addition method

Sl. no.	Number of observations (N)	Amount present (pure) (mg)	Amount of drug added (mg)	Total amount of drug obtained by calculation (mg)	Amount of drug obtained by calculation (mg)	XY	X ²	Recovery (%)
			X	(mg)	Y			
1.	3	0.959	0.988	1.977	0.973	0.961	0.976	
2.	3	0.959	1.982	2.982	1.983	3.930	3.928	
3.	3	0.959	2.985	3.971	2.951	8.809	8.910	99.42
4.	3	0.959	3.978	4.986	3.961	15.757	15.824	
	$\Sigma N = 12$		$\Sigma X = 9.933$		$\Sigma Y = 9.868$	$\Sigma XY = 29.459$	$\Sigma X^2 = 29.638$	

Table 6. Recovery studies of Norfloxacin by standard drug addition method

Sl. no.	Number of observations (N)	Amount present (pure) (mg)	Amount of drug added (mg)	Total amount of drug obtained by calculation (mg)	Amount of drug obtained by calculation (mg)	XY	X ²	Recovery (%)
			X	(mg)	Y			
1.	3	0.965	0.990	1.982	0.880	0.871	0.980	
2.	3	0.965	1.968	2.973	1.970	3.877	3.873	
3.	3	0.965	2.963	3.967	2.969	8.797	8.779	99.62
4.	3	0.965	3.992	4.981	3.967	15.836	15.936	
	$\Sigma N = 12$		$\Sigma X = 9.913$		$\Sigma Y = 9.786$	$\Sigma XY = 29.381$	$\Sigma X^2 = 29.568$	

Table 7. Recovery studies of Ornidazole by standard drug addition method

Sl. no.	Number of observations (N)	Amount present (pure) (mg)	Amount of drug added (mg)	Total amount of drug obtained by calculation (mg)	Amount of drug obtained by calculation (mg)	XY	X ²	Recovery (%)
			X	(mg)	Y			
1.	3	0.983	0.960	1.979	0.954	0.916	0.922	
2.	3	0.983	1.919	2.977	1.903	3.652	3.683	
3.	3	0.983	2.880	3.970	2.854	8.220	8.294	99.25
4.	3	0.983	3.836	4.981	3.811	14.619	14.715	
	$\Sigma N = 12$		$\Sigma X = 9.595$		$\Sigma Y = 9.472$	$\Sigma XY = 27.407$	$\Sigma X^2 = 27.614$	

lin and cloxacillin sodium has been determined by liquid chromatography and norfloxacin is determined by Infra Red spectroscopy There is no method reported for the determination of cefixime and ornidazole in Indian Pharmacopoeia edition-2008

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